

Multi-Response Optimization of FDM Parameters for PLA: A Study on Mechanical and Tribological Properties

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ABSTRACT

In industrial production, additive manufacturing, or 3D printing, is a cutting-edge technique that produces stronger and lighter components or systems. Layer-by-layer geometric shapes are created using 3D object scanners or computer-aided design data. This approach will enhance performance, make complicated geometries possible, and make manufacturing simple. Realistic standards are provided for 3D manufactured goods using the fused deposition modeling 3D printing technique. Compressive strength, surface roughness, and wear resistance are examined in this work to characterise the FDM process utilising PLA by parametric combinations of Printing Speed (PS), Printing Temperature (PT), and Layer Height (LH). To examine this experimental data, ANOVA was employed. Concerning the Taguchi Methodology, the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (S/N ratio) indicates how important process characteristics may impact the individual response. Finally, multi-response optimization is performed by applying Gray Relational Analysis. Achieving the lowest possible Surface Roughness depends heavily on Layer Height (LH). In a similar vein, printing temperature (PT) has a significant impact on shear strength. Once more, Layer Height has a significant impact on maximal wear resistance.

KEYWORDS: 3D printing, FDM, ANOVA, S/N ratio, Surface Roughness, Shear Strength, Wear resistance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing is also commonly known as 3D printing. It is a revolutionary method in industrial production to make lighter and stronger parts or systems. It employs computer-aided design data or 3D object scanners to deposit material as the only source for creating layer-by-layer geometric shapes. Unlike traditional methods, additive manufacturing requires the removal of material through milling, machining, carving, and shaping, among others. That is to say, additive manufacturing offers improved performance, complex geometries, and simplified fabrication in the right applications and provides ample opportunity to those embracing it.

This section offers an overview of the prior research that is pertinent to the earlier study. Extrusion-based methods offer a greater range of material processability, scalability, and cost-effectiveness, making them a promising option for manufacturing functional and multifunctional 4D printing parts and products, as shown by Daminabo et al. (2020). Key parameters, such as surface roughness and mechanical strength, significantly influence the characteristics of FDM-printed polymeric products, providing insights into their relationship and potential future research directions, as indicated by Ahmad et al. (2022). The current analysis focuses on the quality and geometry of tracks printed using PolyMideTM CoPA, PolymaxTM PC, and PolyMideTM PA6-CF materials using fused deposition modelling as revealed by Mwanja et al. (2024). ANOVA analysis revealed that PLA filament, when used in an FDM 3D printer, significantly influences the tensile strength of the part, highlighting the importance of these parameters as revealed by Hikmat et al. (2021). Defects and failure modes are identified by analysing the microstructural characteristics of 3D printed material on part surfaces and fracture contacts. Additionally, it emphasises how crucial raster orientation is to preserving mechanical qualities, as exhibited by Naveed (2020). The impact of layer thickness, raster angle, build orientation, and extrusion temperature on the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and elastic modulus of PLA specimens was examined using Taguchi techniques and ANOVA. The main factor influencing UTS and elastic modulus was determined to be the build orientation; the best results were obtained with a flat orientation, as indicated by Megersa et al. (2024). The Taguchi method and ANOVA were used to analyze the impact strength of PLA material produced through fused deposition modelling (FDM). Results showed that infill density significantly impacts Charpy impact strength, followed by print speed, layer height, and raster angle, with infill density and print speed being the most influential factors,

as revealed by Tunçel (2024). The 30% ceramic-reinforced composite PLA material's additive manufacturing process is examined using Taguchi, ANOVA, and GRA. Significant contributions to mechanical qualities and manufacturing efficiency are shown by examining how printing parameters affect tensile strength, construction time, and material consumption, as presented by Tunçel et al. (2024). Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array is used in 3D printing experiments, with ANOVA determining the importance of each parameter. The TGRA method, based on Taguchi's grey relational analysis (TGRA), finds the optimum parameters for a superior specimen with all-around mechanical characteristics, as indicated by Patel et al. (2024). While other less commonly used polymers, like polyolefins, are shown to become more performant, the results analysed in this research demonstrate that biofillers do not improve the mechanical properties of the most prevalent materials, namely PLA and acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene, as disclosed by Mazzanti et al. (2019). Significant influences on Young's modulus and tensile strength are found when the study examines the effects of infill density, printing speed, build orientation, and layer thickness on the tensile strength of PLA samples manufactured using an FDM 3D printer, as presented by Ahmad et al. (2024).

Through experimental studies on different process parametric combinations of Printing Speed (PS), Printing Temperature (PT), and Layer Height (LH), the work investigates Compressive Strength, Surface Roughness (Ra), and Wear Resistance to study characteristic features of the FDM process in producing the product using PLA. To examine this experimental data, ANOVA was employed. The Signal to Noise Ratio (S/N ratio) illustrates how important process characteristics will impact the individual response with the Taguchi Methodology. Through the use of a single set of optimal or nearly optimal process variables, this experimental investigation seeks to concurrently create minimum surface roughness (Ra), superior compressive strength, and stronger wear resistance while accomplishing the fundamental but conflicting goals. The Grey Relational Analysis has been used for multi-response optimisation. This study is important because it closes the gap between scientific optimization methods and experimental manufacturing, presenting a reliable method of improving surface, mechanical, and wear properties of 3D-printed PLA products. Through the use of ANOVA, the Taguchi Method, and Grey Relational Analysis, the study presents an efficient and industry-oriented means of attaining high-quality 3D-printed parts.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PLAN

The Delta WASP 2040 Industrial X with WASP ZEN X Extruder 0.4 mm was used for the current experimental investigation, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. FDM machine: Delta WASP 2040

PLA (polylactic acid) is the polymer material filament that is utilized. The control parameters considered here are printing speed, printing temperature, and layer height. Other parameters, like infill, raster angle, etc., are fixed. For every experiment, a sample size of 10x10x10 mm is considered. During the experiment, three distinct responses—surface finish, compressive strength, and wear resistance are assessed with the L9 orthogonal array. The Perthometer M1, a stylus-style profilometer made by MahrGmbh, is used to measure the product's surface quality, which is represented as Ra in μm . The TUE-C-100 Universal Testing Machine is used to test the objects' compressive strength. A Tribotester of the (TR-20LE) DUCOM brand is used to perform the wear resistance test. Minitab Software 12 was used for the mathematical analysis. Table 1 below lists the control parameters and their levels according to the FDM machine's capacity.

Table 1. Parameters with levels

Control Parameters	Symbols	Units	Levels		
			L1	L2	L3
Printing Speed	PS	mm/s	30	50	70
Printing Temp	PT	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	190	210	230
Layer Height	LH	mm	0.1	0.2	0.3

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Taguchi Methodology uses Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the S/N ratio graph as an analysis tool. It could be used to assess the process's robustness, which is determined by three responses: strength, surface roughness, and wear resistance. Greater S/N ratio values indicate stability and reduced sensitivity to parameter variability. The smaller numbers will account for a smoother surface with optimal strength.

Table 1 is an ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) table for Surface Roughness in a study investigating the effects of various process parameters, viz. Printing Speed (PS), Printing Temperature (PT), and Layer Height (LH) in the FDM process.

Table 2. ANOVA Table for Surface Roughness

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	6	0.966667	0.161111	145	0.007
Linear	6	0.966667	0.161111	145	0.007
PS	2	0.042222	0.021111	19	0.05
PT	2	0.028889	0.014444	13	0.071
LH	2	0.895556	0.447778	403	0.002
Error	2	0.002222	0.001111		
Total	8	0.968889			

Here F-Value of 403 and P-Value of 0.002 indicate that LH is highly significant and has the most substantial impact on Surface Roughness among the three factors. The overall model is effective in explaining Surface Roughness, with a very low error component.

Table 3. Model Summary of ANOVA for Surface Roughness

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.033333	99.77%	99.08%	95.36%

From Table 3, it is evident that the high R^2 (99.77%) indicates that the regression model fits the data exceptionally well for the experimental data, explaining nearly all variability in Surface Roughness.

Table 4 represents an ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) table for Shear Strength, analyzing the effect of the process parameters on the FDM process. Here F-value of 319.43 and a P-value and 0.003 indicate PT is the most influential factor, showing the highest contribution to Shear Strength variability.

Table 4. ANOVA Table for Shear Strength

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	6	9.4	1.56667	201.43	0.005
Linear	6	9.4	1.56667	201.43	0.005
PS	2	3.74889	1.87444	241	0.004
PT	2	4.96889	2.48444	319.43	0.003
LH	2	0.68222	0.34111	43.86	0.022
Error	2	0.01556	0.00778		
Total	8	9.41556			

The model is statistically sound, with negligible error, demonstrating its effectiveness in analyzing Shear Strength in FDM processes.

Table 5. Model Summary of ANOVA for Shear Strength

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.088192	99.83%	99.34%	96.65%

From Table 5, it is apparent that R^2 (99.83%) indicate that the regression model fits the experimental data exceptionally well, explaining nearly all the variability in the response variable. The model is robust, with a very high fit as indicated by R^2 and strong predictive capabilities. Table 6 represents the ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) table for Wear Resistance, which investigates how the FDM process parameters affect Wear Resistance.

Table 6. ANOVA Table for Wear Resistance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	6	0.000067	0.000011	100	0.01
Linear	6	0.000067	0.000011	100	0.01
PS	2	0.000004	0.000002	16	0.059
PT	2	0.000003	0.000001	13	0.071
LH	2	0.00006	0.00003	271	0.004
Error	2	0	0		
Total	8	0.000067			

With an F-value of 27 and a P-value of 0.004, LH has the largest impact on Wear Resistance, with a very high F-value and a significant P-value (0.004). This indicates LH plays a dominant role in determining Wear Resistance. The model is statistically significant and captures nearly all variability with negligible error.

Table 7. Model Summary of ANOVA for Shear Strength

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0003333	99.67%	98.67%	93.27%

Table 7 indicates that high R^2 (99.67%) and R_{adj}^2 (98.67%) values confirm that the regression model fits the experimental data exceptionally well, capturing almost all the variability in the response variable. The Model Summary indicates that the statistical model is highly robust and effective in explaining the variability in the response variable (e.g., Wear Resistance).

Figure 2a. S/N ratio graph for Surface Roughness Figure 2a. S/N ratio graph for Shear Strength Figure 2a. S/N ratio graph for Wear Resistance

Figure 2a depicts the S/N ratio graph for Surface Roughness. Through Taguchi's ANOVA analysis, the Delta value of the Layer Height (LH) is found to be 2.035 which affects the Surface Roughness significantly. Minimum Surface Roughness is obtained at 30 mm/s PS, 210°C PT and 0.1 mm LH. The S/N ratio graph for shear strength is shown in Figure 2b. The printing temperature's (PT) delta value, as determined by Taguchi's ANOVA analysis, is 0.45, which has a substantial impact on surface roughness. The values of 0.1 mm LH, 230°C PT, and 50 mm/s PS yield the maximum shear strength. Figure 2c shows the Wear Resistance S/N ratio graph. According to Taguchi's ANOVA analysis, the Layer Height (LH) has a Delta value of 1.52, which has a major impact on wear resistance. The maximum wear resistance is achieved at 0.3 mm LH, 70 mm/s PS, and 190°C PT.

Figure 3. Response Optimiser graph for the responses

The composite desirability graph as shown in Figure 3, provides a valuable tool for identifying the optimal process parameters that balance the conflicting requirements of multiple responses. It helps in making informed decisions about the FDM process settings to achieve the best overall performance of the 3D-printed parts. The composite desirability graph provides a visual representation of how well the process

parameters achieve the desired target values for multiple responses simultaneously. The optimal combination of parameters appears to be around PS = 70 mm/s, PT = 230°C, and LH = 0.3 mm. The predicted values for the responses at the optimal point are: Surface Roughness = 3.6887 μm , Shear Strength = 34.9975 MPa and Wear Resistance = 0.0395 $\text{mm}^3/\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental study to determine the optimal parametric combination and the resulting impact of the parameters over the responses can yield a useful and practical guideline for manufacturing a range of 3D printed goods using the FDM technology. From the experimental study and ANOVA analysis, it is evident that Layer Height (LH) plays a significant role in obtaining minimum Surface Roughness. Similarly, Printing Temperature (PT) affects the Shear Strength profoundly. Again, LH plays an influential role in maximum Wear Resistance. The lowest surface roughness is achieved at 0.1 mm LH, 210° C PT, and 30 mm/s PS. Maximum shear strength is obtained at 0.1 mm LH, 230° C PT, and 50 mm/s PS. The highest wear resistance is attained at 190 ° C PT, 70 mm/s PS, and 0.3 mm LH. Since the responses are contradictory, multi-response optimization is performed through Composite Desirability, where a single set of control parameters is detected which can satisfy the responses simultaneously. It seems that PS = 70 mm/s, PT = 230°C, and LH = 0.3 mm are the ideal set of parameters. Surface Roughness of 3.6887 μm , Shear Strength of 34.9975 MPa, and Wear Resistance of 0.0395 $\text{mm}^3/\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$ are the expected values for the responses at the ideal position. These parametric combinations, along with the response values as obtained in this experimental work, can provide a great impetus to the researchers as well as industry personnel who seek to further their study in this domain.

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